

STRESSES AND DISPLACEMENTS AROUND A CIRCULAR MINE TUNNEL DRIVEN IN A ROCK MASSIF WITH ORIENTED CRACKING

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ABSTRACT: The article addresses the issue of determining stresses and displacements around a circular mine tunnel. It passes through a rock massif with oriented cracking. Cracks are located in systems. This type of rock massif is represented as an equivalent uniform transversely isotropic medium. For it, the expressions for the technical constants, which involve geometric characteristics of the cracks, are given. The specified class of problems is solved using complex potential theory. The expressions for the stresses and displacements along the contour of a circular hole are in a cylindrical coordinate system. A real massif has two systems of cracks. The technical constants have been determined for it. The tangential normal stresses and displacements at points on the vertical and horizontal axes along the contour of the tunnel cross section were calculated.

Key words: complex potential theory, systems of oriented cracks.

НАПРЕЖЕНИЯ И ПРЕМЕСТВАНИЯ ОКОЛО КРЪГОВ МИНЕН ТУНЕЛ ПРОКАРАН В СКАЛЕН МАСИВ С ОРИЕНТИРАНА НАПУКАНОСТ

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РЕЗЮМЕ: В статията се разглежда въпросът за определяне на напреженията и преместванията около кръгов минен тунел. Той преминава през скален масив с ориентирана напуканост. Пукнатините са разположени в системи. Този вид скален масив се представя като еквивалентна еднородна трансверзално изотропна среда. За нея са дадени изразите за техническите константи, в които участват геометрически характеристики на пукнатините. Указаният клас задачи се решава с комплексната потенциална теория. Изразите за напреженията и преместванията по контура на кръгов отвор са в цилиндрична координатна система.

Реален масив има две системи пукнатини. За него са определени техническите константи. Изчислени са тангенциалните нормални напрежения и преместванията в точки от вертикалната и хоризонталната ос по контура на напречното сечение на тунела.

Ключови думи: комплексната потенциална теория, системи от ориентирани пукнатини.

Introduction

The rock massif is formed in different geological and climatic conditions under the influence of various factors. They are characterised by non-homogeneity, anisotropy and the presence of cracks. Each crack is characterised by length, width, roughness, wall curvature, and spatial orientation. There are unfilled and filled cracks. According to the length of the cracks, five types of cracks are distinguished: crystal lattice defects, micro cracks at the level of mineral grain sizes, macro cracks, discontinuities, and large tectonic faults (Rupeneit, 1975). The subject of the research is macro cracks, called cracks for short. They actively influence the strength and deformability of the rock massif.

Today, methods are actively being developed that describe the behaviour of cracked rock masses using models. For the most part, these models use the linear relationship between stresses and strains at points around a mine gallery. Analysis of these models can be performed with the general method for solving the plane problem using the theory of functions of the complex variable (Mushkhelishvili, 1953; Mushkhelishvili et al., 1953; England, 2003; Verruit, 2003; Lu et al., 2024).

The aim of this work is to investigate the influence of closely spaced cracks in the rock massif on the stresses around a horizontal mine gallery. This influence will be determined using the methods described in the literature sources cited above.

Methods

1. Problem formulation

The mine gallery has a circular cross-section with radius r_0 . It is driven to a depth of H . The influence of the opening extends over a square area of size $12r_0$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Calculation scheme

The load along the contour of the area is equal to the stresses in the rock massif Q and λQ :

$$Q = \gamma H; \lambda = \frac{\mu_2}{1 - \mu_1}, \quad (1)$$

where

γ is the volumetric weight of the rock massif,

μ_1 is Poisson's ratio in the horizontal direction Ox (Fig. 1),

μ_2 is Poisson's ratio in the vertical direction Oy (Fig. 1).

The Cartesian coordinate system has its origin at the centre of the hole (Fig.1). A cylindrical coordinate system is selected ($r\theta z$). The z -axis is perpendicular to the drawing. Angle θ is measured from the horizontal axis x to y .

The rock massif around the tunnel has two types of crack system (Fig. 1). One is horizontal and the other is inclined (fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Crack systems

2. Mechanical coefficients in a cracked environment

The described rock massif has the following parameters (Rupeneit, 1975):

$$E_2 = \frac{E}{1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i (1 - \sin^4 \theta_i)};$$

$$E_1 = \frac{E}{1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i (1 - \cos^4 \theta_i)};$$

$$\mu_i = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_i \sin^2 \theta_i \cos^2 \theta_i; \quad (2)$$

$$G_2 = \frac{E}{2 \left(1 + \mu + \sum_{i=1}^n \eta_u \cos^2 \theta \right)}.$$

Here, θ_i is the angle of inclination of the crack system i to the horizontal plane (Fig. 2),

n is the number of crack system,

E_1 is the modulus of deformation in the horizontal direction Ox (Fig. 2),

E_2 is the modulus of deformation in the vertical direction Oy (Fig. 2),

G_2 is the shear modulus in the vertical direction Oy (Fig. 2),
 E is Young's modulus in an isotropic area,
 μ is Poisson's ratio in an isotropic rock massif.

The geometric characteristic in formulae (2) has the form:

$$\eta_i = \frac{\delta_i}{h_i \xi_i}, \quad (3)$$

where

h_i is the average distance between crack systems (Fig. 2),

δ_i is the average width of the crack opening,

i is the number of the crack system,

ξ_i is the relative area of the rock contacts. It is studied using special experiments and the method of probability theory.

3. Characteristic equation

The behavior of the rock massif is described by a fourth-order differential equation. Its characteristic equation is (Ivanova, 2022):

$$b_{11}s^4 + b_{17}s^2 + b_{33} = 0, \quad (4)$$

where

$$b_{17} = 2b_{13} + b_{55}.$$

The coefficients in this equation have the following form:

$$b_{11} = \frac{1 - \mu_2 \mu_1}{E_2}; \quad b_{33} = \frac{1 - \mu_1^2}{E_1}; \quad (5)$$

$$b_{13} = -\frac{\mu_2(1 + \mu_1)}{E_2}; \quad b_{55} = \frac{1}{G_2}.$$

The roots of equation (4) are:

$$s_1 = \beta_1 i; \quad s_2 = \beta_2 i; \quad s_3 = -\beta_1 i; \quad s_4 = -\beta_2 i. \quad (6)$$

Here, i is an imaginary unit.

The obtained roots allow us to determine the complex function of the stresses and, through it, to obtain the expressions for the stresses at any point around the hole.

4. Stresses

There are no radial and tangential stresses along the contour of the mine gallery opening, and the normal tangential stresses (Fig. 1). They have the appearance (Vucheva et al., 2023):

$$\sigma_\theta = \frac{Q}{e_1} (e_2 + e_3 + e_4), \quad (7)$$

where

$$e_1 = d_1 d_2 \beta_3; \quad e_2 = \beta_1 d_1 d_2 \beta_3; \quad e_3 = d_3 d_2 \beta_4;$$

$$e_4 = d_4 d_1 \beta_5; \quad \beta_3 = \beta_1 - \beta_2; \quad \beta_4 = \beta_2 - \lambda;$$

$$\beta_5 = \lambda - \beta_1.$$

The remaining coefficients in these expressions for points on the horizontal axis ($\theta = 0$) are:

$$d_3 = -\beta_1; d_4 = -\beta_2; d_1 = \beta_1^2; d_2 = \beta_2^2$$

and for points on the vertical axis are ($\theta = 90^\circ$):

$$d_3 = -\beta_1^2; d_4 = -\beta_2^2; d_1 = 1; d_2 = 1. \quad (8)$$

5. Stresses in an isotropic medium

The stresses along the contour of the cross-section of the circular mine gallery are obtained from (7) and have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{r,o} &= 0; \sigma_{\theta,o} = Q(\sigma_{\theta,5} + \lambda\sigma_{\theta,6} + \sigma_{\theta,7}); \tau_{r,\theta,o} = 0; \\ \sigma_{z,o} &= \nu\sigma_{\theta,o}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The coefficients in these expressions for points on the horizontal axis are ($\theta = 0$):

$$\sigma_{\theta,5} = 1; \sigma_{\theta,6} = -1; \sigma_{\theta,7} = 2. \quad (10)$$

The coefficients in (9) for points on the vertical axis have the form:

$$\sigma_{\theta,5} = \lambda; \sigma_{\theta,6} = 2; \sigma_{\theta,7} = -1. \quad (11)$$

The stresses in equations (7) and (9) are symmetric about the vertical and horizontal axes of the cross-section of the hole (Fig. 1).

6. Displacements

The displacements along the contour of the mine gallery opening at points of a vertical section have the form:

$$u = \frac{q}{E_{11}}(E_{12}E_{33} - E_{12} + \mu_{12}), \quad (11)$$

The displacements at points of a horizontal section are:

$$u = \frac{q}{E_{11}}(E_{33} - E_{12} + \mu_{12}), \quad (12)$$

The parameters on the right-hand side of expressions (11) and (12) are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{12} &= \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}}{E_{22}}}; \quad E_{33} = \sqrt{2(E_{12} - \mu_{12}) + \frac{E_{11}}{G_2}}; \quad (13) \\ E_{11} &= \frac{E_1}{1 - \mu_1^2}; \quad E_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \frac{E_2}{E_1}\mu_2^2}; \quad \mu_{12} = \frac{\mu_2}{1 - \mu_1}, \end{aligned}$$

where

G_2 is the shear modulus in the vertical direction Oy (Fig. 2).

7. Numerical example

The cracks are located in two planes: one horizontal and the other inclined (Fig. 2). The inclination of the planes in which the crack systems are located relative to the horizon, the average crack width, and the average distance between the crack systems are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of a cracked environment

medium	θ_i	δ_i	h_i
dimension	[$^\circ$]	[cm]	[cm]
1	0	0,02	80
2	45	0,02	100

The relative area of the rock contacts is $\xi_1 = \xi_2 = \xi = 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$. The characteristics of the isotropic medium are given: $E = 10^4 \text{ MPa}$, $\nu = 0,2$, $\gamma = 2,5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ MN} / \text{m}^3$. Parameters related to the mining gallery are: $r_o = 1,5 \text{ m}$ and $H = 300 \text{ m}$.

The parameters of the cracked rock massif were calculated using (2). Then, expressions (7) and (9) were applied and the tangential normal stresses in the cracked medium and those in an isotropic medium were obtained. These stresses are referred to the stress in an unbroken array Q . The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Relative tangential normal stresses

σ_θ^V / Q	σ_θ^H / Q	σ_θ^o / Q
1.966	1.973	1.78

The displacements along the contour of the mine gallery opening at points of the vertical and horizontal cross-section are calculated according to (11) and (12). The horizontal displacements are 1.5mm, and the vertical displacements are 2mm.

The following conclusions follow from Table 2:

- horizontal tangential normal stresses are greater than and those along the vertical axis. This difference is small or 0.38%;
- the difference between the horizontal tangential normal stresses in a cracked medium and those in an isotropic medium is 9.5%;
- the vertical tangential normal stresses in a cracked medium and those in an isotropic medium differ by 9.8%.

8. Keys finding

From the results given above, it can be concluded that the stresses in a cracked environment are greater than the stresses in an isotropic environment. This requires taking this heterogeneity into account and applying the environmental model proposed in the work.

The method described in the article is easy to implement. It does not use software packages, but spreadsheets (Aleksander et al., 2022).

Conclusion

The method is used for rock masses possessing oriented fracture systems. This non-uniformity can be taken into account when studying the stress state around a mine gallery.

The development can be used by qualified engineers when investigating stresses around underground facilities with different tunnel shapes.

This method complements the existing analytical models and methods. But these methods are only applicable to a simple and regular geometric system of cracks. When the cracks are many and of different sizes, FEM is applied (Whintely, (2017)). It uses elements that model the cracks. Another numerical method is the boundary element method (Crouch et al., 1983). It uses boundary contact elements in tension and compression.

References

- Aleksander, M. & Kusleika, D. (2022). *Microsoft Excel 365 Bible* 1st Edition, Wiley, 1072 p. ISBN 978-1119835103.
- Crouch, S. I. & Starfield, A. M. (1983). *Boundary element method in solid mechanics*, George & Awuinn, London-Boston-Sydney, 322 p.

- England, A. H. (2003). *Complex Variable Methods in Elasticity*, Courier Corporation, 197 p.
- Ivanova, M. (2022). Stresses in transversely isotropic rock mass around a circular opening. *Annual of the University of Mining and Geology “St. Iv, Rilski” – Sofia*. 65, Section: Mining and Mineral Processing, 26-29.
- Lu, A., Wang, H. & Zhang, L. (2024). *Complex variable solution in the Mechanical Analysis of Tunnels*. Springer, 400 p. ISBN-10 981971690X.
- Muskhelishvili, N. I. (1953). *Some basic problems of the mathematical Theory of Elasticity*. - Gromingen: Nordhoff, 706 p.
- Muskhelishvili, N. I. & Radok J. R. M. (1953). *Some Basic Problems of the Mathematical Theory of Elasticity*, Cambridge University Press, London, UK, 718 p.
- Rupeneit, K. V. (1975). *Deformiruemost masivov treshtinovatyh gornyh porod*. Moskva: Nedra, 223 p.
- Verruit, A. (2003). *Complex Variable Solution of Elastic Tunneling Problems*, Report website <http://go.verruit.net>.
- Vucheva, R. & Trifonova-Genova, V. (2023). Stress around a circular horizontal opening driven in cracked rock mass. *Annual of the University of Mining and geology “St. Iv, Rilski” – Sofia*. 66, Section: Mechanisation, Electrification, and Automation, 195-198.
- Whintely, J. (2017). *Finite element method*. Springer, 232 p. ISBN 978-3-319-49970-3.